

Original Research Article

Knowledge of School Teachers about Infectious Diseases and the Nutritional Status of Children in Schools of Abbottabad

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Abstract

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Teachers play an essential role in giving health education to school children about proper nutrition. If their food lacks the required number of calories, it will lead to malnutrition. Same goes for educating students about infectious diseases at school. A teacher who knows the signs of malnutrition can take care of his/her students effectively. He/she would notice the signs of deficiency of any micro or macro-nutrient much before it triggers deleterious effects to the child's health. It may also affect other children, teachers and parents by spreading and can affect their working ability. We can control the spread of many infectious diseases by giving proper knowledge and training to teachers. A knowledgeable teacher would be able to identify a disease in any of his students in the very early period of infection. He If there is a contagious disease, the teacher's role will be of immense importance in saving other children from catching that disease. This study was conducted with objectives to assess the knowledge of school teachers about nutrition and infectious diseases, and to compare the knowledge among government and private school teachers. This curriculum based cross sectional descriptive study was designed and selected as convenient sampling technique to be carried out at different schools of district Abbottabad. Data was collected by means of an interview-based questionnaire, which was then computed into statistics using SPSS software and the results were interpreted. The overall knowledge of school teachers was not as good as it should be. A large proportion of teachers had never attended any health program, but majority of them expressed desire to attend such programs if they got an opportunity. The knowledge of government teachers was better than those of private sector schools. Majority of the teachers were aware of the importance of nutrition and infectious diseases knowledge. They wanted that knowledge about child health should be added to the curriculum at the school level. Our study concluded that the knowledge of school teachers needs to be improved a lot. For this purpose, health programs and seminars should be conducted in schools or may be short courses to improve the level of knowledge.

Keywords: Abbottabad, Child health, Infectious diseases Malnutrition, Nutrition, Teachers

INTRODUCTION

Teachers play an essential role in giving health education to enrich their students with skills for disease-free living and taking healthy diet. Educating of school children about proper nutrition is very important. If their food lacks the required number of calories, it will lead to

malnutrition. On the other hand, excessive eating will lead to overweight and obesity. Same goes for educating students about infectious diseases at school (Charlton, 2012). In our society the awareness level of communicable diseases, perspective towards education

of changing life style of students and amount of knowledge able to deliver health education by the teachers related to communicable diseases is less than average. Even though they very well know it was a better way to educate their students against communicable diseases, they are still reluctant to educate their students about modifying their lifestyle. One problem is, that the teachers aren't well equipped in the field of training and skill to deliver such education. The education of teachers about healthy lifestyle shouldn't be limited to simple advice and informing, there is room to improve teachers' awareness of communicable diseases in our country (Yee et al., 2015).

Most of the children receive their nutrition from the food at the school. It is important for the food programs such as those in the schools to be sufficient in calories. According to Centre of Disease Control (CDC), less calorie intake can lead to poor physical health. If a child receives a diet other than the balanced diet, it will affect the ability of the child's brain to function properly (Nancy and Johnson, 2014).

School going children exhibit a two to three times larger risk of getting infections, which influences both individual health and on the propagation of infections through the community. Between other factors, the risk is dependent upon the properties of schools. The transmission of diseases can be controlled through simple preventive measures, including proper cleansing of hands after exposure, using special safety measures, cleanliness of changing room, cleaning and disinfection of polluted places, separate people and kitchens for management of foods, reports of infectious diseases, training of employees and guidance for parents (Nesti and Goldbaum, 2011). The quality of both father- and teacher-child relationships were found to have a direct association with children's prosaically behaviour. The teacher should be able to listen to the child's problems and should have enough knowledge to educate him about personal hygiene.

In our country, the school lunch and breakfast programs do not exist in majority of schools. The students get their nutrition from snacks like potato chips and sugar sweetened beverages and confectionary which is also known as junk food (Bano et al., 2013). They have irregular eating habits and the concept of balanced diet is considered unimportant.

There are many schools in Abbott bad district including primary, secondary and high schools. Forty three per cent (43%) of the population are children up to 15 years of age. The middle and upper-class families can afford private schools while the low-income families enrol their children in the government schools. Good research studies about the nutritional status of school children in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK) are few. The aim of this project is to have an insight of nutritional status and infectious diseases of the children at schools of Abbottabad

LITERATURE REVIEW

Global

Nutritional status of school children

In the US, a state of urgency exists regarding the eating behaviour of children. Children consume fast food instead of the nutrient rich foods such as vegetables and fruits. According to a survey conducted in 2003 the nutritional status of the boys from age 14-18 years which met the USDA approved quantity of fruit and vegetable intake was only 0.7%. Special attention is necessary to control the increasing rates of overweight and obesity in children and adolescents. Illustrative of this, obesity rates have doubled among children and tripled among adolescents in the last 2 decades. In the US, 30.1% of children and adolescents, aged 2 through 19 years, were at or above 85% of body mass index (BMI) for age based on 2003-2006 data from the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (Briggs et al., 2010).

They are taking measures to adjust the nutrient intake in schools and colleges, ensuring that the foods provided to kids in colleges are in keeping with current dietary recommendations is a very important national focus. The National College Lunch Program (NSLP) and the college Breakfast Program (SBP) hold the potential to supply nearly all the nation's schoolchildren with access to alimentary, inexpensive meals to support their growth, development, and health. The NSLP alone is accessible in 99% of U.S. public colleges and in 83% of personal and public colleges. In year 2007, the taking part colleges served regarding five.1 billion lunches at a federal price of roughly \$8.7 billion (Stallings et al., 2010).

In London, about 10% of the school going children are obese and more 20-25% are overweight. Studies estimates that by the year 2025, about 40% of the Briton population are going to be obese. They are reviving new techniques like nutrition education for children in gaming pattern like the "Top Grub" and "A Healthy Eating", including lessons about nutrition in the school syllabus and training the teachers to educate the students about hazards of un-healthy diet (Lakshman et al., 2010).

South Africa's high incidence of malnutrition severely affects children's well-being and ability to learn. According to the World Bank, malnutrition is in the households, schools and practically all occupations of life because the teachers and parents are not well informed about healthy food choices and feeding practices. One major cause of the problem is that the income of the families in Africa is low and most families are poverty stricken which renders them from providing healthy nutrition for their children. WHO, the world bank and other organizations are working to improve the lifestyle of the area through health education and providing means to fight malnutrition and infectious diseases. A long-term solution to the problem is to encourage people to grow

food and improve their incomes, but a quicker solution is to provide health and nutrition education and services to encourage healthy food choices (Oldewage-Theron and Napier, 2011).

In Asia, some countries are poverty stricken and some are comparably developed, hence both malnutrition and overweight and obesity is present. The nutrition of school going children is poorly managed as the caregivers don't have enough knowledge of dieting. Data from the Malaysian School-Based Nutrition Survey (MSNS), comprising a nationally representative sample of school-going children aged 10 to 17 years, were used. The overall prevalence of physically inactive adolescents was 57.3%. Afternoon school session, breakfast consumption (no breakfast and irregular breakfast), body mass index status (obese and underweight), and body weight perception (underweight perceivers) were significant factors associated with physical inactivity among Malaysian adolescents. There is evidence of different programs which promote nutritional education at the household, school, and community levels (Mian et al., 2012).

Infectious diseases

In North America, the phrase “infectious diseases of poverty” (IDoP) is used to describe infectious diseases that are more common amongst poor and susceptible populations mostly children and teenagers. IDoP comprises HIV and AIDS, TB, and malaria—the “big 3” (also referred to as the “Unholy Trinity”); and neglected tropical diseases (NTDs). Poverty has been indistinguishably linked with infectious diseases since the early ages. Poverty, working through non-genetic heritable principles, has transformed infectious diseases into “inheritable” conditions (Hansen and Painsil, 2016).

Evidence-based pointers for the management of patients with methicillin-resistant staph aureus (MRSA) infections were ready by associate professional Panel of the Infectious Diseases Society of America (IDSA). The rules are meant to be used by health care suppliers UN agency look after adult and medical specialty patients with bacterial infections like cellulitis, pruritus, methicillin resistant staphylococcus aureus (MRSA), nodules, impetigo, urinary tract infections (UTIs), endocarditis, pneumonia, bone and joint infections, and central nervous system (CNS) infections (Liu et al., 2011).

In Europe, the common infections in children are GIT infections caused by Shigela, non-typhoidal Salmonella, Campylobacter, vibrio cholera, enterotoxigenic Escherichia Coli and Clostridium difficile. These infections are associated with dehydration and loss of weight because of diarrhoea. Department of Translational Medical Science, Section of Paediatrics, University of Naples Federico II, Naples, Italy after a series of surveys considered diseases like TB, Measles, Poliomyelitis etc. as non-existent in Europe (Guarino et al., 2014).

Present standing and issues of infectious diseases in African kids are elaborate. The Department of paediatrics, Mie University faculty of medicine has ten years' expertise of international medical cooperation with African countries. At present, the department is taking part in two projects in Africa and Zambia. The activities are dispensed within the field of priority infectious diseases in African kids. Major infectious diseases in Africa are malaria, diarrhoea, acute respiratory infections and some specific parasitic diseases like kala azar (a leishmania donovani infection). Acquired Immuno-deficiency Syndrome (AIDS) has additionally become a threat to the health and survival of kids in Africa. To cut back morbidity and mortality owing to these diseases, primary health care activity is also an efficient and economical measure (Hori et al., 1993).

In South Asia, Preventable infections are a significant reason for deaths and disabilities. Over 2/3rd of the calculable 3.7 million deaths in children in South Asia within the year 2000 were because of infections like respiratory disease, diarrhoea, and measles. India currently has the second largest population with AIDS and Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) infection within the world, and chronic diseases like tuberculosis (TB) and hepatitis still threaten the lives of millions. Of the burden of deaths associated with infectious disease within the region, around 63% in youngsters aged below five years. Serious effort ought to be dedicated to the management of communicable disease if South Asian countries are to fulfil their millennium development goal of 2/3rd reduction in child mortality by 2015 (Zaidi et al., 2004).

NATIONAL

Nutritional status of school children

In Pakistan, the average income of the families is below the poverty line. Most of the children are malnourished although some children who belong to rich and uneducated families are overweight and even obese. A Study was carried out to determine the nutritional status of school going children living in Islamabad, Pakistan. The study revealed a high prevalence of malnutrition among these children. The prevalence of malnutrition was higher amongst older children and those from households which were poorer and had many members. It is now recommended to include school going children of the country in the Pakistan National Nutrition Survey (Mian et al., 2012). It is prompt that a comprehensive strategy be enforced in developing countries, particularly Pakistan, so as to forestall child under-nourishment. Additional to poverty alleviation, the underlying causes that employment against food security, food safety, women education, safe facility, sanitation and adequate

health care should be self-addressed (Anwer and Awan, 2013).

Infectious diseases

Poor hygiene, low literacy rate of the parents, poverty and lack of proper health education in schools renders our children susceptible to different sorts of infections (Baqir et al., 2012). Many diseases are common in Pakistan including epidemic and endemic infections. These are TB, hepatitis, malaria, AIDS/HIV infection, dengue fever, poliomyelitis, rabies, diarrhoea, skin, eye infections, leptospirosis, leishmaniosis respiratory infections (Baqir et al., 2012; Sultan and Khan, 2013) and measles. Every year about half a million people die from malaria. Dengue outbreaks in Karachi, Swat and Lahore tested an already stretched Health system and diverted resources from other priorities after media attention (Sultan and Khan, 2013).

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

1. To assess the knowledge of teachers about nutrition and infectious diseases in school of Abbottabad.
2. To compare the knowledge of teachers among various schools of Abbottabad.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design

It is a cross sectional study.

Population under study

School teachers serving in government and private schools of district Abbottabad

Study Tool

An interview-based questionnaire (Appendix) was designed to assess knowledge of school teachers about nutrition and infectious diseases. It was pre-tested to rule out any discrepancies and difficulties by conducting interviews from some teachers of Ayub Medical College. It contained questions regarding names of infectious diseases, modes of transmission, causative environmental factors and association with nutritional and socioeconomic status of children together with questions on important nutritional aspects of school going children.

Sampling Technique

Permission letters, explaining the purpose and requirements of study, signed by college authorities were sent to all schools of Abbottabad. Institutes that allowed us for conduction of this research were visited. Teachers were informed in detail about nature and purpose of interview and subsequent study being conducted. Consent was given by those who agreed to participate and interviews were taken.

Inclusion Criteria

Teachers who gave consent were added in this study.

Exclusion Criteria

Teachers who did not give consent were excluded.

Sample Size

Total 173 school teachers participated in interview sessions out of which 90 belonged to private sector and 83 belonged to government sector schools of Abbottabad.

Classifying Knowledge

No knowledge: Teachers who gave no answer.

Bad knowledge: Teachers who answered with only one option.

Satisfactory knowledge: Teachers who answered with 2 options.

Good knowledge: Teachers who answered with 3-5 options.

Excellent knowledge: Teachers who answered with 6 or more options.

Knowledge Of Teachers

Studies show that teachers do not have enough knowledge about the diseases and nutrition of the students. The reasons include lack of proper training programs for the teachers, less teaching experience (mostly less than 5 years) and the customary belief that health and education are different things and the school has nothing to do with the child's health. Moreover, it was also concluded that the teachers were not optimistic to teach the students about modifying their lifestyle (Yee et al., 2015).

Table 1. Characteristics of government and private school teachers according to their gender, experience and qualifications

Characteristics	Valid	Government	Private	Total
Gender	Male	38 (21.9%)	23 (13.2%)	61 (35.2%)
	Female	45 (26.0%)	67 (38.7%)	112 (64.7%)
	Total	83 (47.9%)	90 (52.0%)	173 (100%)
Experience	0-5	16 (09.2%)	64 (36.9%)	82 (47.3%)
	6-10	07 (04.0%)	16 (09.2%)	23 (13.3%)
	11-15	14 (08.1%)	05 (02.8%)	18 (10.4%)
	16 & above	46 (26.5%)	04 (02.3%)	50 (28.9%)
	Total	83 (47.9%)	90 (52.0%)	173 (100%)
Qualifications	Matric	4 (02.3%)	0 (00.0%)	04 (02.3%)
	F. A/F. Sc	9 (05.2%)	0 (00.0%)	09 (05.2%)
	Bachelors	10 (05.7%)	13 (07.5%)	23 (13.3%)
	Masters	44 (25.4%)	72 (41.6%)	116 (67.0%)
	PhD	16 (09.2%)	5 (02.8%)	21 (12.1%)
	Total	83 (47.9%)	90 (52.0%)	173 (100%)

Figure 1. Percentage of participants knowing/not knowing about infectious diseases

RESULTS

The knowledge of government and private school teachers about nutrition and infectious diseases is shown in table 1.

Teachers were asked whether they knew about infectious diseases or not. The results are shown in figure 1. P- Value .058

Grading of knowledge of respondents based upon number of infectious diseases stated by them is shown in table 2.

Participants were asked about modes of transmission of infectious diseases, the results are shown in figure 2. P-value: .031

Different water borne diseases mentioned by teachers are shown in table No. 3.

Some of the important modes of transmission of infections stated by teachers during the interviews are given in the table 4.

According to the participants, the most important environmental factors influencing spread of infectious diseases are given in table 5.

Table 2. Examples of infectious diseases

Valid	Government	Private	Total	P value
No knowledge	10 (%)	18 (10.4%)	28 (16.1%)	0.073
Bad	26 (15.0%)	28 (16.1%)	54 (31.2%)	
Satisfactory	23 (13.2%)	28 (16.1%)	51 (29.4%)	
Good	17 (09.8%)	12 (06.9%)	29 (16.7%)	
Excellent	7 (04.0%)	4 (02.3%)	11 (06.3%)	
Total	83 (47.9%)	90 (52.0%)	173 (100.0%)	

Figure 2. Percentage of participants knowing/not knowing about modes of transmission of infectious diseases**Table 3.** Frequency of water borne diseases

Diseases	Government	private	Total
Diarrhoea	58 (38.5%)	57 (32.9%)	115(66.5%)
Hepatitis	31 (17.9%)	22 (12.7%)	53(30.6%)
Typhoid	27 (15.6%)	17 (9.8%)	44 (25.4%)
Cholera	18 (10.4%)	14 (8.1%)	32 (18.6%)
UTIs	06 (3.5%)	07 (4.0%)	13 (7.5%)
Skin infections	05 (2.9%)	11 (6.4%)	16 (9.5%)
Food poisoning	08 (4.6%)	20 (11.6%)	28 (16.2%)
Malaria	10 (5.8%)	10 (5.8%)	20 (11.6%)
RTIs	01 (0.6%)	07 (4.0%)	08 (4.6%)
Tuberculosis	03 (1.7%)	00 (0.0%)	03 (1.7%)

Table 4. Mode of transmission

Mode	Government	Private	Frequency
Contact	33 (19.1%)	33 (19.1%)	66(38.2%)
Cough	25 (14/5%)	20 (11.6%)	46 (26.7)
Contaminated food	15 (8.7%)	11 (6.4%)	26 (15.0%)
Contaminated water	21 (12.1%)	17 (9.8%)	38 (22.1%)
Respiratory droplets	42 (24.3%)	34 (19.7%)	76 (43.9%)
Sexual transmission	03 (1.73%)	08 (4.6%)	11 (6.4%)
Saliva	11 (6.4%)	11 (6.4%)	22 (12.7%)
Sharing articles	27 (15.6%)	16 (9.2%)	43 (24.9%)
Contaminated syringes	05 (2.9%)	09 (5.2%)	14 (8.1%)
Surgical instruments	02 (1.2%)	03 (1.73%)	05 (2.9%)
Human and animal wastes	02 (1.2%)	04 (2.3%)	06 (3.1%)
Blood transfusion	05 (2.9%)	12 (6.9%)	17 (9.6%)
Vectors	02 (1.2%)	01 (0.6%)	03 (1.7%)

Figure 3. Percentage of participants who think there is/is not a relationship between environmental factors and infectious diseases. P-value is .829**Table 5.** Environmental factors

Factors	Government	Private	Frequency
Pollution	60 (34.7%)	67 (38.7%)	127(73.4%)
Contaminated soil	14 (8.7%)	07 (4.0%)	21 (12.1%)
Stagnant water	28 (16.2%)	24 (13.9%)	52 (30.1%)
Mosquitoes	01 (0.6%)	01 (0.6%)	02 (1.2%)
Unhygienic conditions	10 (5.8%)	13 (7.5%)	23 (13.3%)
Overcrowding	07 (4.0%)	04 (2.3%)	11 (6.4%)
Poor sanitation	13 (7.5%)	11 (6.4%)	25 (14.5%)
Radiations	07 (4.0%)	11 (6.4%)	05 (2.9%)
Hospital wastes	01 (0.6%)	02 (1.2%)	03 (1.7%)
Smoke	20 (11.6%)	17 (9.8%)	37 (21.4%)
Pollen	12 (6.9%)	14 (8.7%)	26(15.0%)

Figure 4. Percentage of participants knowing/not knowing about diseases caused by inadequate nutrition

Table 6. Disease related to inadequate nutrition

Disease	Government	Private	Total
Anaemia	20 (11.5%)	18 (10.4%)	38 (22.0%)
Kwashiorkor	9 (5.2%)	3 (1.7%)	12 (06.9%)
Marasmus	7 (4.0%)	2 (1.1%)	09 (05.2%)
Goitre	6 (3.4%)	1 (0.5%)	07 (04.0%)
Rickets	9 (5.2%)	4 (2.3%)	13 (07.5%)
Arthritis	2 (1.1%)	2 (1.1%)	04 (02.3%)
Scurvy	2 (1.1%)	3 (1.7%)	05 (02.9%)
Night blindness	2 (1.1%)	1 (0.5%)	03 (1.70%)
Stunted growth	10 (5.7%)	31.7 (%)	13 (07.5%)
Mental retardation	7 (4.0%)	6 (3.4%)	13 (07.5%)
Osteoporosis	18 (10.4%)	22 (12.7%)	40 (23.1%)
Others	8 (4.6%)	7 (4.0%)	19 (09.9%)

155 (89.5%) participants think that there is a strong relation between economic status of children and malnutrition, out of which 78(45.0%) belonged to government sector and 77(44.5%) belonged to private sector.

154 (89.0%) of them could recognize general sign and symptoms of malnutrition in school going children, out of which half of them belonged to government sector and half belonged to private sector.

78 (45.0%) private school teachers and 70 (40.4%) government school teachers believed that improper nutrition can add to the development and spread of infectious diseases.

Teachers were asked about the diseases which are caused by inadequate nutrition. Results are given in figure 4. P value is .451

The participants were asked about diseases caused by inadequate nutrition and their answers are summarized in table 6.

A question, asked about the sources of minerals and vitamins, reproduced the following result as shown in the diagram. Only 6.4% participants knew enough sources, which could be labelled as "Good knowledge". There was no significant difference between government and private sectors.

All the participants mentioned milk as a vital component of children's diet. Almost 95% of them recommended 1-2 glasses/day while the remaining 5% recommended more than 2 glasses.

Some important related questions which were asked are shown in the following tables.

Figure 5. Grading of knowledge of school teachers regarding sources of vitamins and minerals

Table 7. Health seminars/workshops attended

Questions	Government		Private		P value
	Yes	No	Yes	No	
Participants who attended health programs in past.	25 (14.5%)	58 (33.5%)	22 (12.7%)	68 (39.3%)	.405
Participants who wish to attend health programs in future.	67 (38.7%)	16(9.2%)	75 (43.4%)	15 (8.7%)	.657
Participants who knew about importance of isolation in infectious diseases.	67 (38.7%)	16(9.2%)	76 (44.0%)	14 (8.1%)	.521

Table 8. Opinion of teachers about their school healthcare system

Questions	Government		Private		P value
	Yes	No	Yes	No	
Teachers who mention health risk in classrooms	69 (40.0%)	14 (8.1%)	76 (44.0%)	14 (8.1%)	.816
Teachers who are in favour of specific subjects on nutrition and infectious diseases	77 (44.5%)	6 (3.4%)	86 (50.0%)	4 (2.3%)	.436
Basic facility in school	39 (22.5%)	44 (25.4%)	64 (37.0%)	26 (37.0%)	.001
Teachers who are satisfied with the level health care facility in school	24 (14.0%)	59 (34.1%)	58 (34.0%)	32 (18.5%)	.000

DISCUSSION

Teachers have the key role as educators and advisors in any society; hence the study was aimed to assess the knowledge and attitude of teachers towards nutrition and infectious diseases and to compare the knowledge of private and government school teachers. Knowledge about infectious diseases is shown to be high in several studies from developed as well as developing countries

(Homi et al., 2014) which matches our findings as the result (figure 1) shows the majority of teachers had knowledge about infectious diseases. Although there were some misconceptions about certain diseases and the quality of their knowledge was mostly satisfactory (Table 2), a large fraction of them could answer questions about infections and about their modes of transmission. Some of the teachers (mostly private in schools) didn't know about the modes of transmission and prevention of

infectious diseases (Figure 2, 4).

Malnutrition among school going children is due to inadequacy of one or more of the three requirements viz food, care and health. Previous studies support the link between economic status and malnutrition in children (Sunil and Singh, 2014). 89% of the teachers consider poor economic status to be the reason for malnutrition and infections in children. The students of government's school belong to poor families which is why malnutrition is more common in government school children than private schools.

Environment plays an important role in prevalence of infectious diseases in children. In government schools, the students belong to poor families, the classes are more congested and unhygienic conditions which are risk factors for infections and its easy spread. The private school on the other hand are well maintained and have fewer students.

There was no significant difference between the government and private school teachers about the knowledge of modes of transmission of infectious diseases. Most common modes of transmission of infectious diseases mentioned by the teachers are respiratory droplets, contact, cough, contaminated water and sharing articles (Table 5).

Water borne diseases are some of the most prevalent infectious diseases in school going children. In India, 18% of child mortality age 6-14 years are due to diarrhoea alone (Lakshminarayanan and Jayalakshmy, 2015). Some of the water borne diseases mentioned by the teachers are; diarrhoea, hepatitis, typhoid and cholera. Majority of the teachers from both sectors knew enough about water borne diseases. A similar study shows that 66% of the teachers heard about infections, 68% knew about different modes of transmission of infectious diseases and most of them considered environmental factors to influence the transmission of communicable diseases (Bilal et al., 2010).

Majority of the teachers (89.0%) from both sectors could identify the major sign and symptoms of malnutrition (78.0%) were of idea that inadequate nutrition can play an important role in the spread of infection since immunity becomes weak if one does not take a balanced diet. Diet deficient in essential nutrients is important underlying risk factor for deaths due to infectious diseases.

Only a handful of teachers from both sectors have attended workshop or conference related to health services. This shows the need of such seminars and health conferences in the country. A study shows that the teacher's knowledge improved to surprisingly 18% from previously 11% (Guerriero, 2013). Less than half of the teachers were aware of the concept of isolation of infected children, though the government school teachers have better ideas about isolation than the private ones (Table 7).

Although many government and private school teachers said that they have basic health facilities in their schools yet the condition of health services provided there was not satisfactory. In some schools, not even a first aid kit was available. During this study only one such school having complete school health service was present. The health care facilities in schools of both sectors were inadequate but the condition of government schools condition can be considered more deteriorating as far as hygiene, overcrowding and other such factors are concerned (Table 8).

The level of knowledge about nutritional health of the children and infectious diseases, experience and academic qualification of government school teachers was better than those of the private schools' staff.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that the knowledge of most of teachers about nutrition and infectious diseases is not adequate despite high qualifications. The knowledge of government school teachers is better than those of private school teachers. Most of the teachers did not get an opportunity to attend a health program although they are aware of the importance and want to attend such programs. The basic health facility in the schools like emergency room or first aid roometc. are also not satisfactory and need to be improved.

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